

ISic0467

I.Sicily inscription 0467

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

urn

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Caltanissetta

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Caltanissetta, serving as a water basin in Norman church of S. Spirito, outside Caltanissetta (so
NSA)

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. T(iti) · Flavi · Aug(usti) · lib(erti)

2. Diadumeni

3. Flavia · Victorina

4. patri · pissimo

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491695

EDCS 21900530

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7189 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 68-69

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 50

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